

NEWSLETTER

Welcome to CONCILIARE: Advancing Our Research

Welcome to the second edition of the CONCILIARE newsletter!

Dear colleagues, as our project progresses, we are pleased to share updates on our activities, upcoming events, and new resources. This newsletter aims to serve as a platform to promote the project's activities, parallel events, and ongoing research, keeping partners and collaborators informed and connected.

Project Website Now Live!

We are excited to announce that the CONCILIARE website is now live! The website features an introduction to our team members, project updates, upcoming events, and a 'Resources' section, where relevant materials will be made available. This section includes relevant publications with research results closely related to CONCILIARE, contributed by project members and renowned international researchers. We encourage you to visit, share, and follow the latest developments.

[READ MORE](#)

Additionally, we invite you to stay connected by following our Instagram and Facebook pages to keep up with our latest updates and activities. Your engagement is essential in broadening the reach of our research.

UPCOMING EVENTS

CONCILIARE Annual Meeting 2025

We are pleased to announce the CONCILIARE Annual Meeting 2025, which will take place at the Institute of Social Sciences Ivo Pilar in Zagreb, Croatia. The event will feature a plenary session discussing the results, challenges, and future activities of the project, as well as Individual WP Meetings, the General Assembly, and the Executive Board Meeting.

 March 19-20, 2025

 Zagreb, Croatia

(De)Colonial Visions: Dialogues in Visual Culture, Alterities, and Activisms – a joint event by CONCILIARE, MigraMediaActs, and the SOPCOM Visual Culture Working Group.

This one-day event, held in Portuguese and English, will bring together scholars, artists, and activists to foster critical conversations about the colonial past and its enduring impact on contemporary society. The event will be in a hybrid format, with in-person and online participation options available.

 April 28, 2025

 Braga, Portugal

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

Deliverable 1.1 of Work Package 1

We are pleased to announce that the Technical Report for WP1 – Deliverable 1.1 has been successfully completed. "*Textbooks: Changing Colonial Cultural Heritage with Confidence*" has been delivered by the University of Helsinki, University of Coimbra, and University of Rome La Sapienza. Congratulations to everyone involved in this achievement!

Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Best regards,

Júlia Vilhena, Rosa Cabecinhas, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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